

InterAgency Institute
BEYOND INSTITUTIONAL BOUNDARIES

ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION FOR REGENERATIVE DEVELOPMENT.

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Policy Statement

This policy brief analyzes the importance of the correlation between Environmental Education and the learning path of children and young people to promote integrated and regenerative territorial development in mining areas. The importance of this correlation is already enshrined in Sustainable Development Goal No. 04, which, in proposing the guarantee of quality education, includes the development of the skills needed to promote sustainable development. In the context of mining areas, due to the economic, political, and social complexity of it, this perspective becomes even more relevant. Therefore, to guarantee integrated and regenerative territorial development, from the perspective of the coevolution of socio-economic and environmental systems, it is necessary to implement Environmental Education in a systemic, critical, and daily manner, not only in informal education environments but also in formal education environments, i.e., in public and private schools, specifically in their curriculum standards.

Background

The premise that education could be a way of spreading knowledge and contributing to environmental protection initiatives gained prominence in the 1960s (Wetering et al., 2023). During this decade, scientists began to draw attention to growing ecological problems, such as the contamination of water, soil, and land and the destruction of natural resources, which required greater public awareness (Gough, 2016). These problems were formally recognized in 1972 at the United Nations Conference on the Human Environment, which reinforced the need for more information about the condition of the environment and the importance of Environmental Education (Gough, 2016). Later, in 1977, the first intergovernmental conference on Environmental Education was held by the United Nations Education, Scientific, And Cultural Organization (Unesco) in partnership with the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP). On this occasion, the Tbilisi Declaration was promulgated, establishing the initial principles for Environmental Education [1], which generally focus on promoting public and global knowledge about environmental issues and encouraging the development of individual skills for the protection and improvement of the environment (Wetering et al., 2023).

As the complexity of environmental issues has increased, this initial understanding has had to be broadened, encompassing not only environmental issues but also social, political, and economic issues and strengthening a critical approach towards sustainability. In this regard, the Principles of Education for Sustainable Societies and Global Responsibility are worth highlighting, more specifically, the values such as cooperation, equal rights, autonomy, democracy, and participation, which permeate the principles that "must be present in sustainability-oriented education" (Crespo, 1998). The process of implementing Environmental Education, rather than being hierarchical, competitive, and exclusivist, should emphasize cooperation, participation, and the generation of autonomy for the actors involved, in line with a perspective of integrated and regenerative territorial development that presupposes coevolution between human and natural systems, to promote mutual benefits for all (Becker, 2023).

This raises the challenge of implementing this approach to Environmental Education not only in the institutional structure but also in the daily practices of communities. Children and young people, as opinion formers and decision-makers concerning the future (UNICEF, 2022), should be the primary target audience of this process. The school, a formative institution still central to societies, should be the locus of this constructive process (Uhde et al., 2021, pp. 115-116).

The inclusion of Environmental Education in schools enables children and young people to learn to take a stand on environmental issues and their intersections with political, economic, and social issues. A school where its staff shares these values is more likely to have them understood by the students. In addition, the school should be seen as an impacting unit within a larger context. It should work on the actual reduction of such impacts both as part of a social need and as an activity to develop commitment and skills to deal with such problems. Besides educational purposes, the process should be part of solving the municipality's real problems, based on the contribution of each of these impacting units (which can be an individual, institution, etc.) to maintaining or solving these problems. This process will only be complete when its content and principles are incorporated into the curriculum, i.e., institutionally integrated into the student's learning process (Andrade, 2000).

Findings

Over the years, various political-legal provisions have been improved. Environmental education programs for children and teenagers have been implemented both in schools and in non-formal education spaces (i.e., research centers and museums) (Wetering et al., 2023) to try to advance the implementation of environmental education from a perspective that integrates it with the student's learning process.

Internationally, this commitment is expressed in SDG 4, which seeks to guarantee quality and inclusive education for all, including environmental education. Other goals, such as SDG 12 (which aims to ensure sustainable production and consumption patterns), SDG 13 (which focuses on measures to combat climate change and protect ecosystems), and SDG 15 (which aims to protect forests, biodiversity, and ecosystems) also strengthen this commitment. All these SDGs are related to environmental education and the protection of the environment, directly or indirectly linking the learning process to the promotion of sustainability and setting the target that, by 2030, "all students will acquire the knowledge and skills necessary to promote sustainable development" (UNDP, 2015).

In the European Union, Member States consider climate change to be one of the most severe problems facing the world today. The education and training sector, like all sectors, should take measures to respond to this global crisis. The European Commission supports EU Member States in their efforts to (European Commission, 2022):

- Provide learners and educators with the knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary for a greener and more sustainable economy and society.
- Support education and training institutions in integrating sustainability into teaching and learning and all aspects of their operation.
- Create a shared understanding of the profound and transformative changes needed in education and training for sustainability and the ecological transition.

In January 2022, the European sustainability competence framework ("GreenComp") was published and translated into all official EU languages. It may be used in education and training programs and policies in formal, non-formal, and informal contexts.

The framework defines the four groups of competencies related to sustainability that should be acquired by students of all ages (European Commission, 2022):

- (1) Embodying sustainability values, including the competencies valuing sustainability, supporting fairness, and promoting nature.
- (2) Embracing complexity in sustainability, including the competencies of systems thinking, critical thinking, and problem framing.
- (3) Envisioning sustainable futures, including the competencies of futures literacy, adaptability, and exploratory thinking.
- (4) Acting for sustainability, including the competencies of political agency, collective action, and individual initiative. In 2023, the Commission created the community of practice to connect schools, researchers, public authorities, and other bodies through the new competencies framework.

In the Brazilian context, based on an institutionalization process that began in the 1980s with the enactment of the National Environmental Policy (Law No. 6.938 of 31/08/81) [2], general competencies that all students should develop. In other words, every student should be able to "Act personally and collectively with autonomy, responsibility, flexibility, resilience, and determination, making decisions based on ethical, democratic, inclusive, sustainable and solidarity principles" (BNCC, 2017). The inclusion of Environmental Education among the competencies of the BNCC is highly relevant since the BNCC is the normative document that defines the organic and progressive set of essential learning skills that all Brazilian students must develop throughout their primary education (BNCC, 2017). In the context of Brazilian formal education, Environmental Education requires an interdisciplinary and transversal approach that enables students to develop not only a systemic view of the concept of sustainability (Instituto Unibanco, 2019) but fundamentally enables students to develop a practice that integrates environmental, economic, social, political, and cultural aspects throughout their learning journey. This perspective imposes a mission on school principals and teachers to surpass a one-off approach to the subject and to establish and propose connections that consider the community's surroundings and daily life (Movimento pela Base, 2023), especially in the context of ecosystems impacted, for example, by mining activities, to ensure that the environment is a subject included in the curriculum more organically and permanently. Thus, initiatives that propose, for example, the construction of a curriculum framework that integrates the learning skills provided for in specific areas of knowledge (i.e., Languages, Mathematics, Natural Sciences, and Human Sciences) with the learning skills for the

development of Environmental Education, the proposal of field research with the subsequent collective development of a student action plan to resolve an environmental issue identified in the community (Instituto Unibanco, 2019), and actions that propose intervention in the environment by the students (i.e., the construction of gardens and greenhouses) (Uhde et al., 2021, pp. 123-124) are possible ways of implementing Environmental Education in the student's learning path.

Recommendations

The initiatives investigated, both internationally and nationally, indicate that ensuring compatibility between environmental education and the student's learning path, with the aim of integrated and regenerative territorial development, should be a priority in education and training policies and programs, as already proposed by the Council of the European Union in its recommendation on learning for ecological transition and sustainable development (European Council, 2022).

As the Council of the European Union has pointed out, all students must be given opportunities to study and experience sustainability in formal education (i.e., schools and higher education), based on a compatible curriculum, and in non-formal education (i.e., extracurricular activities and youth work) (European Council, 2022).

Furthermore, there is a need to create learning environments conducive to sustainability that cover all the activities and areas of operation of an educational establishment and enable practical, interdisciplinary teaching and learning relevant to local contexts (European Council, 2022).

Conclusions

The link between environmental education and other "educations," such as education for sustainable development and citizenship, among others, in the context of the 2030 Agenda and the challenges of diversity and equity, requires an interdisciplinary, collaborative, and systemic approach, which calls for communication and coordination between teachers and subjects. In addition to building a curriculum framework that integrates the learning skills provided for in specific areas of knowledge (i.e., Languages, Mathematics, Natural Sciences, and Human Sciences) with the learning

skills for developing Environmental Education, the collaboration of different educational agents should be sought in the analysis of problems/difficulties and the development and evaluation of proposals for solutions as another effective way of improving Environmental Education in specific contexts.

In this regard, the emphasis on action, the transformation of practices, and the potential of implementing projects in this area involve, on the one hand, looking inside the school and its day-to-day strategies for managing environmental resources, including a variety of recycling, reuse and reduction practices, the implementation of mechanisms to ensure greater energy efficiency or the redistribution of resources. On the other hand, beyond the school walls, it requires engaging in learning activities centered on real-life problems, allowing students to identify possible causes and solutions. This knowledge they develop is then used for collective actions of democratic problem-solving, i.e., initiatives in which the students try to inform and mobilize the community towards more ecological behaviors. By engaging in these actions, they recognize themselves as producers of knowledge (and not just consumers of knowledge).

From this same perspective, action projects - as mentioned above, supported by local authorities and higher education institutions - may link scientific research with local community problems, allowing participants to contextualize the knowledge acquired in the classroom in a way that connects the school to the real world.

References

Andrade, Daniel Fonseca de. (2000). *Implementação da Educação Ambiental em Escolas: uma reflexão*. Revista Eletrônica de Educação Ambiental. V. 4. Access 10/22/2023.

Becker, Luzia Costa. (2023). *Da política minerária à (in) segurança hídrica dos territórios: a concertação interações e o papel do Estado na defesa do desenvolvimento integrado e regenerativo*. Zenodo. Access em 10/10/2023. Available <<https://zenodo.org/records/8169838>>.

Brasil. (2017). *Base Nacional Comum Curricular. 2017*. Access 10/12/2023. Available <<http://basenacionalcomum.mec.gov.br/>>.

Brasil. (1988). *Constituição da República Federativa do Brasil*. Brasília: Senado, 2012.

Brasil. (2002). Decreto n. 4.281, de 25 de junho de 2002. Regulamenta a Lei no 9.795, de 27 de abril de 1999, que institui a Política Nacional de Educação Ambiental, e dá outras providências. Access 10/10/2023. Available <<http://www.prograd.ufu.br/legislacoes/decreto-no-4281-de-25-de-junho-de-2002-educacao-ambiental#:~:text=Resumo%3A,Ambiental%2C%20e%20d%C3%A1%20outras%20provid%C3%AAs>>.

Brasil. (1996). *Lei nº 9.394, de 20 de dezembro de 1996*. Estabelece as diretrizes e bases da educação nacional. Access 10/10/2023. Available

<https://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/leis/l9394.htm#:~:text=L9394&text=Estabelece%20as%20diretrizes%20e%20bases%20da%20educa%C3%A7%C3%A3o%20nacional.&text=Art.%201%C2%BA%20A%20educa%C3%A7%C3%A3o%20abrange,civil%20e%20nas%20manifesta%C3%A7%C3%B5es%20culturais.>.

Brasil. (1997) Ministério da Educação e Cultura/Secretaria de Educação Fundamental. *Parâmetros Curriculares Nacionais: Meio ambiente e saúde*. Brasília, v. 9. BRASIL.

Brasil. (1999). *Lei nº 9.795, de 27 de abril de 1999*. Brasília, DF: Subchefia para assuntos jurídicos.

Brasil. Ministério do Meio Ambiente. Política Nacional do Meio Ambiente (PNMA). (1981). Lei nº 6.938, de agosto de 1981. Brasília.

Colling, Isadora; Dos Santos, Sarah de Jesus Silva; Siqueira, Sofia Terezinha Rabello. (2022). *Importância da educação ambiental: O papel das escolas na educação climática*. Unicef. Access 10/12/2023. Available <<https://www.unicef.org/brazil/blog/importancia-da-educacao-ambiental>>.

Crespo, Samyra. (1998). Educar para a sustentabilidade: a Educação Ambiental no programa da agenda 21. In: Noal, Fernando Oliveira; Reigota, Marcos; Barcelos, Valdo Hermes de Lima (Org.) *Tendências da Educação Ambiental brasileira*. Santa Cruz do Sul: EDUNISC, p. 211-225.

European Commission. (2022). *Aprendizagem em prol da transição ecológica e do desenvolvimento sustentável*. Access 10/13/2023. Available <<https://education.ec.europa.eu/pt-pt/focus-topics/green-education/learning-for-the-green-transition>>.

European Council. (2022). Council adopts recommendation to stimulate learning for the green transition and sustainable development. Access 10/12/2023. Available <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2022/06/16/council-adopts-recommendation-to-stimulate-learning-for-the-green-transition/?utm_source=dsms-auto&utm_medium=email&utm_campaign=Council+adopts+recommendation+to+stimulate+learning+for+the+green+transition+and+sustainable+development.>.

GOUGH, Annette. *The Emergence of Environmental Education Research: A 'history' of the field*. Melbourne: RMIT University, 2016.

Instituto Unibanco. (2019). Educação Ambiental deve ser trabalhada de forma ampla. *Aprendizagem em Foco*, n. 54. Access 10/20/2023. Available <<https://www.institutounibanco.org.br/aprendizagem-em-foco/54/>>.

Movimento pela Base. (2023). Para entender a Educação Ambiental na BNCC. Access 10/14/2023. Available <<https://observatorio.movimentopelabase.org.br/para-entender-a-educacao-ambiental-na-bncc/>>.

Programa das Nações Unidas para o Desenvolvimento (PNUD). (2015). *Objetivos de Desenvolvimento Sustentável*. Access 10/10/2023. Available <<https://brasil.un.org/pt-br/sdgs>>.

Uhde, Eliane Marili et al. (2021). Práticas de Educação Ambiental em uma escola do campo. *Revbea*, São Paulo, v.16, pp. 114-129.

United Nations Education, Scientific, And Cultural Organization (Unesco); United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP). (1977). *Tbilisi Declaration*. Access 10/10/2023. Available <<https://www.gdrc.org/uem/ee/tbilisi.html>>.

Wetering, Judith van de. et al. (2022). Does environmental education benefit environmental outcomes in children and adolescents? A meta-analysis. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, v. 81. Available <<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0272494422000275>>.

[1] The Tbilisi Declaration established three fundamental principles: 1) to promote awareness of economic, social, political, and ecological interdependence in urban and rural areas; 2) to provide opportunities for everyone to acquire the knowledge, values, attitudes, and skills necessary to protect and improve the environment; and 3) to create new patterns of behavior for individuals, groups, and society as a whole concerning the environment (UNESCO; UNEP, 1977).

[2] After Law n. 6.938/81, the 1988 Federal Constitution recognized the constitutional right of all Brazilian citizens to Environmental Education and assigned the State the duty to "promote Environmental Education at all levels of education and public awareness for the preservation of the environment" (art. 225, §1, item VI). The National Education Guidelines and Framework Law – LDB refers to Environmental Education in article 32, item II, according to which "natural and social environmental understanding of the political system, technology, arts and values on which society is based" is required for Primary Education; and in article 36, paragraph 1, according to which Primary and Secondary Education curriculum "must include (. ...) knowledge of the physical and natural world and the social and political reality, especially of Brazil" (L. 9.394 of 20/12/96). The establishment of the National Environmental Education Policy - PNEA (Law 9.795, of 27/04/99) reinforces and qualifies everyone's right to Environmental Education, indicating its principles and objectives, the actors, and bodies responsible for its implementation in the formal and non-formal spheres, and its main lines of action. Decree no. 4.281, of 25/06/02, which regulated Law no. 9.795/99, details the competencies, attributions, and mechanisms defined for the PNEA, creating the Management Body responsible for its coordination, composed of the Directorate of Environmental Education of the Ministry of the Environment (DEA/MMA), and the General Coordination of Environmental Education of the Ministry of Education (CGEA/MEC).

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